

1 **Deletion of H-ferritin in macrophages mitigates the**
2 **development of steatohepatitis and hepatocellular carcinoma**
3 **in mice**

4 Short title: An effect of H-ferritin deletion on NASH development

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15 **Supplementary Figure legends**

16 Supplementary Figure 1. Inhibitory effect of macrophage-specific FTH deletion on high-
17 fat diet-induced non-alcoholic fatty liver. (A) Representative images of liver sections
18 from WT and KO mice fed a normal diet or high-fat diet (HFD) for 12 weeks (upper: low
19 magnification of hematoxylin-eosin (HE) staining; middle: high magnification of (HE)
20 staining; lower: F4/80 immunohistochemistry). (B) Semi-quantitative scores of steatosis,
21 hepatocyte ballooning, lobular inflammation, and NAS. Values are expressed as the mean
22 \pm SEM (n = 5-6 in each group); *P<0.05 (C) Quantitative analysis of F4/80 positive area
23 and mRNA expression of F4/80 in the liver. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n =
24 6-8 in each group); *P<0.05.

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26 Supplementary Figure 2. Effect of FTH deletion in macrophages on iron content by DAB
27 enhanced Perl staining. Upper panel: Representative images of DAB enhanced Perl
28 staining in the livers of mice from all groups. Lower panel: Semi-quantitative analysis of
29 iron-positive areas. Values are expressed as the mean \pm SEM (n = 4-6 in each group);
30 *p<0.05

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32 Supplementary Figure 3. Effect of macrophage-specific FTH deletion on hepatic ferritin
33 protein expression in normal liver and NASH. Upper panel: Representative protein bands
34 of H-ferritin (FTH), L-ferritin (FTL), and β -actin in the livers of mice; lower panel: Semi-
35 quantitative densitometry analysis of FTH and FTL protein expression. Values are
36 expressed as the mean \pm SEM (n = 11-13 in each group); *p<0.05

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Supplementary Figure 1 Ikeda, et al.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Supplementary Figure 2 Ikeda, et al.

Supplementary Figure 3 Ikeda, et al.

Supplementary table 1. Sets of primer sequences

	Forward	Reverse
Mouse tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α (<i>Tnfa</i>)	ACGGCATGGATCTCAAAGAC	GTGGGTGAGGAGCACGTAGT
Mouse monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (<i>Mcp1</i>)	GGAGCTCATGATGTGAGCAA	GACCAGGCAAGGGAATTACA
Mouse plasminogen activator inhibitor-11(<i>Pai1</i>)	GTCTTTCCGACCAAGAGCAG	GACAAAGGCTGTGGAGGAAG
Mouse transforming growth factor- β 1 (<i>Tgfb1</i>)	CCGGAGAGGAGACTTCACAG	TCCACGATTTCCCAGAGAAC
Mouse collagen-1 (<i>Coll1a1</i>)	CAGGCAGGCAGTATCACTCA	TGTCCTCATCCTGGAAGGTC
Mouse collagen-3 (<i>Col3a1</i>)	ACCAAAAGGTGATGCTGGAC	GACCTCGTGCTCCAGTTAGC
Mouse F4/80 (<i>Emr1</i>)	CTGTAACCGGATGGCAAAC	CTGTACCCACATGGCTGATG
Mouse CD36 (<i>Cd36</i>)	TGCATTTGCCAATGTCTAGC	CCTTAAAGGAATCCCCGTGT
Mouse fatty acid synthase (<i>Fas</i>)	TGCTCCCAGCTGCAGGC	GCCCCGGTAGCTCTGCGTGTA
Mouse SREBP1c (<i>Srebp1c</i>)	TGCGGCTGTTGTCTACCATA	AAGCAGCAAGATGTCCTCCT
Mouse PPAR α (<i>Ppara</i>)	TTGAAGGAGCTTTGGGAAGA	AGAAGTTGCAGGAGGGGATT
Mouse AFP (<i>Afp</i>)	CTCAGCGAGGAGAAATGGTC	GAGTTCACAGGGCTTGCTTC
Mouse GPC3 (<i>Gpc3</i>)	CCCTGAATCTCGGAATTGAA	AGTCCCTGGCAGTAAGAGCA
36B4	GCTCCAAGCAGATGCAGCA	CCGGATGTGAGGCAGCAG

Supplementary table.2 Characterization of Body weight, liver weight, liver deviation enzyme, and hepatic triglyceride in WT mice and LysM-Cre *Fth* KO mice fed either a normal diet (ND)-fed mice or a high fat diet (HFD)

	ND		HFD	
	WT	LysM-Cre <i>Fth</i> KO	WT	LysM-Cre <i>Fth</i> KO
Initial body weight (g)	22.2 ± 0.4	22.5 ± 0.5	21.7 ± 0.4	21.1 ± 0.4
Last body weight (g)	31.9 ± 0.9	28.9 ± 0.6	40.1 ± 1.7***	34.6 ± 1.8#†
Liver weight (mg)	966 ± 31	907 ± 24	1123 ± 49***	868 ± 4††
LW/BW	30.6 ± 1.1	31.0 ± 0.8	27.8 ± 0.6*#	27.1 ± 1.1
Hepatic TG (mg/g tissue)	58 ± 7	40 ± 5	99 ± 12***	64 ± 7†
Hepatic iron (µg Fe/g tissue)	10.0 ± 1.9	7.4 ± 0.5	8.7 ± 0.4	7.4 ± 0.7

Data represent mean ± SEM; *n* = 8-12; **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01 vs. WT-ND; #*P* < 0.05, ###*P* < 0.01 vs. LysM-*Fth* KO-ND, †*P* < 0.05, ††*P* < 0.01 vs. WT- HFD

Supplementary table.3 Characterization of Body weight, liver weight, liver deviation enzyme, hepatic triglyceride, and hepatic iron content in WT mice and LysM-Cre *Fth* KO mice with western diet (WD) combined with carbon tetrachloride (CCl4) and high sucrose (HS)/high glucose (HG) water at 30wks

WD+CCl₄/HF+HG		
	WT	LysM-Cre <i>Fth</i> KO
Initial body weight (g)	22.5 ± 0.2	22.4 ± 0.2
Last body weight (g)	32.0 ± 0.6	31.0 ± 0.4
Liver weight (mg)	2785 ± 132	2068 ± 83**
LW/BW	87.3 ± 4.2	66.7 ± 3.6**

Data represent mean ± SEM; *n* = 11-13; **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01 vs. WT- WD+CCl₄/HS+HG